

Assessing Quality of Various Aspects of Secondary Education in Punjab

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Abstract

This study examined various aspects of quality in secondary education of Punjab. Population of the study was constituted all principals, teachers and students of degree colleges, intermediate colleges and higher secondary schools. A randomized sample of forty degree colleges was selected comprising forty intermediate colleges and forty higher secondary schools (gender-wise equal). Participants' responses were collected via questionnaire. After the data tabulation, it was examined and explained in the light of research objectives. Statistical tests like mean, standard deviation, standard error of mean and estimated population mean were employed. The study revealed that from the findings of the study A.V Aids were not appropriately used, teachers' pay scales were not satisfactory and secondary level curriculum did not meet the academic needs. Therefore, the researchers consider provision of modern audio-visual aids to the institutions to be important, besides the teachers training and motivation to utilize these audio-visual aids for enhancement of instructional process. Moreover, it is suggested that adequate budgetary allocation for education and improving the pay scales of the teachers will enhance the quality of education.

Key Words:

Quality
Education,
Secondary
Education, AV
Aids, Pedagogy

Introduction

It is worthwhile mentioning the continuous change in structure of education along the content. Until 1930's, there was no awareness of secondary education. Tawney, who was the well-known educationist pioneered secondary education in England in 1928. Before this attempt, there was no concept of secondary education, although the Capital of the UK had elementary and higher education. The whole concept of primary education followed by the secondary education was a novel approach and still it seems to be in a new one. Education used to be up to elementary level; whereas acquiring higher education was limited to the rich lot of

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the society that could afford the expenses of institutions and fee. Singh (2000) propounded the notion of entrance examinations termed as intermediate.

Secondary education is one of the key sub segments for the overall education system. Secondary education not only produces work force for the growth of economy but also paves the way for higher education. The standard of higher education is significantly based on the excellence of secondary education. We cannot produce the professionals of high calibre in economic and socio-political life unless we raise the standard of secondary education. Brown (1998) is of the opinion that secondary education may be organized to invigorate both men and women to pursue higher education. It should also inculcate in them the spirit to be adjustable in their practical life meaningfully and effectively. Secondary education based on quality and standard is of great importance to everyone. In plain words, we can say firmly that secondary education has its own status. We also desire that this significant education gets more status than its current relegated case. The quality of higher education is ruled out without standard secondary education. Without the quality of secondary education, we cannot judge the standard of research and development of a nation. Both are directly linked with each other.

Abadzi (1993) in his research has stated that both the quality of a system vis-a-vis the quality of its consumers is interdependent. It is a well-known fact that a society or its citizens define quality according to their own perceptions and make conditions that under which the quality can be established and offered. It is certain that Quality of an institution is referred as the outcome/success rate produced by its individuals. Thus the repute of an institution is solely dependent upon the success rate of that specific institution. Quality education is not possible without quality teachers and the educational institutions where they teach. The quality of an educational institutions is based the significant features of their well versed and skilled teachers, a congenial environment for imparting knowledge and skills and where the results of the examinations are in one way or the other curtailed.

With the creation of Pakistan as new state in 1947, the leaders of the nation attached high significance to evolution of education system so it could guarantee the desired impact. Therefore, the First Educational Conference was arranged in 1947. The founder of the nation in his message emphasized on the right type of education to be imparted to the Pakistani youth. The very message of the Quaid-e-Azam is, "Education does not merely mean academic education. There is immediate and urgent need for such type of education to our people which is according to the needs of time" (Government of Pakistan, 1947).

The Quaid-e-Azam wished Pakistan develop a system of education that approximates to the capabilities of masses and is compatible with with Pakistan's history and culture. He also wished that it should be at par with modernism and rapid development which was going on at that time around the world. Keeping in view the purport of the Quaid's message the Commission brought to the limelight the purpose of an educational system as mentioned, "The educational system is an

instrument, through which a society has to equip all its people to lead productive public lives according to their talents and interests” (Government of Pakistan, 1959).

Farooq (1994) in his research has highlighted that just like other countries of the world, secondary education in Pakistan also not possible to be studied if the societal needs and the needs of the children are properly judged. At this stage, by analyzing the education being provided due importance must be attached to cultural and social values of individuals and to the grooming of the inborn capabilities. It is therefore, inevitable to recognize the national culture and its offshoots in which the learning institutions exist. An added plus is that nature of the learning process must be considered. The competence of any system can only be gauged if secondary level of education taken into consideration in global scenario. There are clear or implied measures or standard indicators in every culture of the quality of education. Mainly these indicators are three with reference to classification. These are:

- Educational inputs
- Educational outputs and
- Educational processes.

Inputs consist of financial; physical as well as manpower measurements linked with the resources which are given to learners in every level of learning. While expenses of education per student usually summarize the financial measures. The third offshoot which is physical measure contains many required material facilities

Murnane (1987) in his study has concluded that manpower or human resource measures include the number of working individuals of various nature, often stated as ratios in respect of the number of the students at each level. These comprise supporting data of the personnel for example educational background, experience and possibly expertise in their related fields.

In the same vein UNESCO (1990) explicitly explained in his review that the process of education is the interaction amongst students, and teachers; the course contents vis-a vis as co-curricular and extra-curricular activities. There are a number of mediating factors that influence the interactions like as assurance and support of the community and parents. Satisfaction of customers and the services being provided about a product is based upon the quality of that particular product (Liston, 1999). The researcher has given defined significant elements about quality approach as following: Identifying and satisfying clients' needs.

- Satisfaction and identification of customers' need
- Improvement and keeping an eye on the potentialities of the employees
- Refinement of major processes.

Farooq (1994) has expressed his views very vividly that results possess the actual measurements of quality in education. In other words, quality should be gauged in the framework of outcomes. A learned individual need to show particular capabilities in particular fields. According to the researcher a well learned

individual is a pragmatic client, very careful and capable man, having sound mind towards the personal liberty and societal responsibilities.

Quddus (1990) argues that quality in education cannot be ensured if the students have the required aptitude and skills for learning. UNESCO (1998) report also emphasise this feature and extend that students are the raw material for education process so they are required to have the skills to cope up with academic as well other problems which arise during their studies. Except for students aptitude quality and other soft skills, the report focuses on the standard of curricula, sufficient infrastructure and availability of standard facilities. Moreover, quality of teachers' training, adopting suitable teaching methodology, use of IT in teaching and learning process are also key points for ensuring the quality of education. In addition, quality of management is also emphasized for maintaining the quality of education (UNESCO, 1998). Currently, majority of the developing countries are worried about the low standard of their secondary education. The situation is particularly grim in Pakistan and the neighboring countries (Sing, 1995). More than fifty percent of the students who appear in secondary or higher secondary examinations fail to qualify for a pass certificate each year.

It is vital to for the improvement of quality of education to focus on the curriculum issues: the number and scope of courses presented at school level as well as content of each subject. The prime issue is encountered by secondary schools in all systems that comprise of both optional and compulsory subjects: that is the proper adjustment between reacting to learners' preferences and utilizing facilities as well as educators productively. The World Bank went to secondary schools in which only nine learners opted for a specific subject. A few schools use certain outstanding teachers as meager as two hours on daily basis. The World Bank proposes that there is need to review precisely the expense of offering subject decision to learners, with the aim to diminish the scope of subjects offered and improving utilization of instructors' time (Kashore, 1990).

The quality of education is connected with teacher's qualifications, curriculum taught, teaching methodologies and physical facilities. The effect of these variables on quality of education may be checked through proper assessment. The performance of the students and teacher is based on their examination results (Government of Pakistan, 1998).

Purpose of the Study

The study explores the quality of education at secondary level in Punjab. Following objectives were framed in the light of the proposed study:

1. To explore the suitability of access to facilities in education for teaching at secondary level.
2. To investigate the value of curricula at secondary level education.
3. To ascertain the appropriateness of instructional media at secondary level.

4. To observe the suitability of in-service training for secondary level teaching.

Research Methodology

The study was designed to evaluate the quality of secondary education in Punjab. All the principals, teachers and students at secondary level in Punjab were constituted the population of the study. A total 60 principals, 300 teachers and 600 students were selected randomly. Data was collected through questionnaires were organized, tabulated, analysed and interpreted in the light of research objectives.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Descriptive and Inferential Analysis of Teachers' Responses Regarding Quality of Secondary Education

Statements	\bar{X}	SD	$SE_{\bar{X}}$	μ
Teachers are provided with inservice training by the Government.	0.87	1.43	0.06	0.76 to 0.98
Job securities is ensured.	0.91	1.62	0.06	0.80 to 1.02
Contract appointments affect teacher's efficiency positively.	-0.10	1.60	0.06	-0.01 to 0.21
Pay scales are excellent that encourage to work hard.	0.47	1.28	0.05	0.38 to 0.56
Teachers are satisfied with their remunerations.	-0.64	1.36	0.05	-0.55 to -0.73
Physical facilities are adequate for teaching	-0.35	1.33	0.05	-0.26 to -0.44
Laboratories apparatus is available	-0.05	1.27	0.05	-0.04 to 0.14
A.V. aids are properly utilized.	-0.72	1.44	0.06	-0.61 to -0.83
A.V. aids are according to the modern needs	-0.60	1.41	0.05	-0.51 to -0.69
Syllabus being taught is according to needs of society.	-0.06	1.18	0.04	-0.01 to 0.13
Curriculum at secondary level meet the societal needs	-0.09	1.14	0.04	-0.02 to -0.16
English as medium of instruction is useful	0.41	1.30	0.05	0.32 to 0.50
Urdu as medium of instruction is useful.	0.51	1.37	0.05	0.42 to 0.60

Table 1 depicts that teachers perspectives to be described nothing that some will have had any expertise and proficiency in any other scheme of education. They have earned degrees under a similar system where they currently perform their duties. Likewise, it must be considered that among them, a large portion well reasonably, consider themselves to be performing well for the studies and be comprehensively contented with their own endeavors. Conversely, they are clearly disappointed with compensation, basic facilities, availability of books and other different resources. They showed disappointment with the best possible utilization of AV aids. It shows lack of training and deficient resources or both. Comparatively, they gave the impression to be pleased with the administration of the principals in the school. While they expressed that they are moving satisfactorily in the direction of the set objectives, they were dissatisfied with the curriculum and syllabuses of their own areas. Further they expressed that curriculum do not meets the needs and demands of the society. However, the instructors imagine that they are completing a outstandingly great job despite the reality that there is some wavering about the standard of educational provision. Perceiving that the examinations from the basic par of assessment, it is to be substantial worry that they are not strongly of the view that the system is reasonable. They were in support of Urdu or English medium of instruction equally. Contrasting their viewpoints, utilizing chi-square as a contingency demonstrates that the perspectives of two dialects are marginally different, with the perspectives on Urdu being more captivated ($\chi^2 = 20.0$ (df4), $p < 0.001$).

Table 2. Descriptive and Inferential Analysis of Students’ Reponses Regarding Quality of Secondary Education

Statements	\bar{X}	SD	$SE_{\bar{X}}$	μ
Teaching staff in the institution is well qualified	1.24	1.48	0.04	1.17 to 1.31
Teachers are well prepared before delivering the lecturer	0.94	1.42	0.04	0.87 to 1.01
Teachers are very regular and punctual in the class	0.80	1.48	0.04	0.73 to 0.87
A.V. aids are properly used in the class	0.45	1.36	0.04	-0.38 to -0.52
Teachers attitude towards students is positive	0.81	1.34	0.03	0.76 to 0.86

Institution has well equipped laboratories	- 0.27	1.42	0.04	-0.20 to - 0.34
Laboratory experiments are performed regularly	- 0.35	1.35	0.04	-0.28 to - 0.42
Laboratories equipment and apparatus is available	- 0.05	1.27	0.05	-0.04 to 0.14
Syllabus being taught is according to the future needs of society	0.25	1.28	0.03	0.20 to 0.30
Sufficient books are available in the library	- 0.15	1.51	0.04	-0.08 to - 0.22
Sufficient computer facilities are available.	0.08	1.44	0.04	0.01 to 0.15
Institution has well established hostel facilities for students.	- 0.95	1.61	0.04	-0.88 to 1.02
English as medium of instruction is useful	0.41	1.30	0.05	0.32 to 0.50
Urdu as medium of instruction is useful.	0.51	1.37	0.05	0.42 to 0.60

Table 2 demonstrates that students are unequivocally of the opinion that teachers work hard but they are not so positive about the use of homework. Their general viewpoints about teachers and their school is good. It will depict general devotion and lack of experience of various systems and standards, and the feelings that they perform their best in order to get success. They are not persuaded about the utilization of laboratory and they obviously desire additional time to do experiments. It may indicate deficient funds as well as resources and additionally poor confidence of instructors in utilizing the resources. Similarly, the utilization of computer is likewise an issue area. They do not think that the AV aids are not very much utilized well affirming their instructors' impressions. There is some concern about the curriculum which do not fulfil their forthcoming requirements. Perceiving that the examinations from the basic par of assessment, it is to be considerable worry that they are not strongly of the opinion that the system is reasonable. They showed an equal support for English as do the instructors but on the other hand, they are significantly more firmly for the utilization of Urdu. It clearly shows that using English is more demanding and requires them to endeavor to learn the dialect to adequately high level.

However, almost 58% are still emphatically of English, this rising to about 82% for Urdu.

Table 3. Descriptive and Inferential Analysis of Principals' Responses Regarding Quality of Secondary Education

Statements	\bar{X}	SD	SE \bar{X}	μ
Building facilities are adequate.	0.04	1.36	0.13	-0.21 to 0.29
Equipments are according to the needs	-0.01	1.26	0.12	-0.22 to 0.24
Laboratories are fully equipped.	-0.25	1.38	0.13	0.00 to - 0.50
Availability of computer facilities is satisfactory.	0.03	1.28	0.12	-0.20 to 0.26
Adequate books are available in the library	0.009	1.28	0.12	-0.22 to 0.23
A.V. aids are according to the contemporary needs.	-0.83	1.60	0.15	-0.54 to -1.12
Hostel facilities are available.	-0.99	1.74	0.17	-0.66 to -1.32
Transport facilities are available.	-1.21	1.74	0.17	-0.88 to - 1.54
Current curricula is par with international standards.	-0.34	1.21	0.11	-0.13 to -0.55
Present curricula help to develop the critical thinking among the students.	-0.24	1.42	0.13	-0.01 to 0.49
Urdu as medium of instruction is useful	0.74	1.45	0.14	0.47 to 1.01
English as medium of instruction is useful	0.13	1.32	0.12	-0.10 to 0.36

Table 3 shows the responses of principals and it can be concluded that only few had experiences in other educational system. They have earned degrees under a similar education system where they currently perform their duties as heads of the institutions. Majority of the principals could evaluate themselves to put their most ideal endeavors for their students. They appear

to be enormously pleased with their own endeavors. They were not happy with the laboratory, transport, library facilities and the building facilities. They likewise did not demonstrate fulfillment over the availability of A.V. aids. Conversely, they showed contentment relating to their teaching workforce. The principals appear to genuinely happy with the standard of instruction at the secondary level as it is uncovered from their general view. The information also shows that there is some type of unrest among the principals regarding curriculum which is completely unsuitable to meet the future needs. They were additionally found to condemn the appraisal system. They were in support of both English as well as Urdu medium of instruction. However, they appeared to increasingly inclined in their support for Urdu. It can be deducted that the utilization of English is significantly more demanding and they are required to learn this global dialect at higher level. Nevertheless, it cannot be refuted that Urdu could be utilized for learning in a better way at intermediate level as it is our national dialect.

Conclusions

1. Maximum respondents viewed that audio visual aids were not applied for instructional purposes in classrooms.
2. Most of the sample respondent were of the view that adequate availability of books were not present in the libraries.
3. Respondent also viewed that pay scales were not up to the mark that would encourage the teachers for hard work.
4. Maximum institutions lacked the physical facilities due to lack of financial resources.
5. Majority of respondents were in favor of urdu be the medium of instruction for better understanding of the concepts.
6. The curriculum of the secondary level were also opposed to the societal needs.

Recommendations

As result of finding of the study recommendations be made as follows.

1. In order to promote better learning procedures the government should fully cooperate in provision of A.V aids to the institutions.
2. The education institutions should be funded for the provision of computer, books and internet facility.

3. The education budget should be increased to a reasonable level for better outcomes in the education field.
4. Before devising curricula for secondary level, the societal need should not be ignored.
5. The institutions should individually be provided financial support to upgrade the physical facilities in order to produce better outcomes.

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